

Furfural hydrogenation, hydrodeoxygenation and etherification over MoO₂ and MoO₃:
a combined experimental and theoretical study

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ABSTRACT

Valorization of lignocellulosic biomass, particularly catalytic hydrotreatment of hemicellulose-based furfural (FUR), has been studied for the production of value-added chemicals. A three-phase batch reactor has been used for hydrotreatment in isopropanol over various commercially available unsupported MoO_x catalysts, at various temperatures (170–230 °C), pressures (0–80 bar H_2), catalyst loadings (0–2 wt.%), and reactant concentrations (5–20 wt.%). No significant difference in catalytic activity or selectivity has been observed among the three different MoO_3 and one MoO_2 catalysts, while $\text{NiMo}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, Mo_2C and WO_3 were much less active. Data-points collected have been used to propose a detailed reaction pathway network for a micro-kinetic model, which also took into consideration the thermodynamics, and adsorption, desorption, and surface reaction kinetics. The alcoholysis of FUR yielded valuable isopropyl levulinate (IPL) as the major product under all tested reaction condition, while other value-added compounds (furfuryl alcohol, isopropyl furfuryl ether, furfuryl acetone, angelica lactone) were observed in smaller quantities. It was found that neither the presence nor the absence of the gaseous H_2 pressure contributes to the global reaction rate, or selectivity, since the solvent acts as a sufficient hydrogen donor. Additionally, density functional theory (DFT) calculations provided further insight into the active planes present, by the implementation of the Wulff construction. Furthermore, the reaction mechanism was explained based on reaction energies, which were *in silico* determined and compared for several surfaces. The results were consistent with the characterization and activity-testing results. The furfural ring-opening reaction, yielding valuable IPL in the absence of gaseous H_2 , over a cheap bulk MoO_x is reported for the first time.

Keywords:

Furfural hydrotreatment

Catalytic alcoholysis

Wulff construction of MoO_x

Micro-kinetic modelling

Density Functional Theory (DFT)

1. Introduction

Through the employment of biomass-derived carbohydrates, the ever-growing problem of using scarce and environmentally unfriendly fossil fuels can be surmounted. Lignocellulosic biomass represents the most promising substitution due to its high abundance, relatively easy acquisition, and a wide array of potentially derived products that find their applications in various fields. Furfural is an important platform chemical that can be easily obtained by hydrolysis of hemicellulosic biomass to form xylose (pentose), which is then subsequently dehydrated to furfural. Agricultural and industrial biomass waste can be converted to furfural using sulfuric, hydrochloric, or phosphoric acid as catalysts with high conversion and moderate yields [1]. Various industrial processes of furfural production were described well in the review by Zeitsch [2]. The oldest one dating from 1921, the Quaker Oats process, allows for furfural production using sulfuric acid and giving yields around 50 %, varying with the respect to the temperature and acid concentration used. Furfural can be produced with slightly higher yields using more complex ionic liquids [3] or homogenous catalyst [4]. More recently, optimization studies involving the use of sulfuric acid under lower pressures and temperatures enabled obtaining furfural yields even up to 88 % [5]. However, challenging separation, the reuse of catalysts and quite hazardous operating conditions pose additional problems. Moderate yields due to various inhibiting side reactions, including retroaldol fragmentation of xylose to C₁₋₄ acids and products degradation to solid humins [6,7] notwithstanding, furfural remains one of the most important platform chemicals whose market share is continually growing and attracts a great attention in the fields of industry and research.

High functionalization of furfural allows for a vast array of possible products upon conversion (furfuryl alcohol – FAL, tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol – THFA, 2-methylfuran – 2-MF, 2-methyltetrahydrofuran – 2-MTHF, furan, tetrahydrofuran – THF, pentanediol,

furfuryl acetate, furfuryl ethers – FE, alkyl levulinates esters – LE). Consequently, a plethora of descriptive review articles have been published on these topics [8–10]. As these products find their applications as fuel additives and value-added chemicals, the research and industry are heavily focused on their properties and various production routes. Additionally, the focus on their production via various catalytic processes (hydrogenation, oxydation, hydrogenolysis, deoxygenation, decarboxylation) is of main concern as a way for increasing economic and environmental efficiencies, while providing the market with innovative, yet much desirable technologies.

Selective hydrogenation of furfural (FUR) to furfuryl alcohol (FAL) constitutes about 65 % of the overall usage of furfural [11], and is mostly done using Pt- [12], Pd- [13], or Cu-Cr-based catalysts in either gas [14] or liquid phase [15]. The environmental issues with chromium toxicity and the usage of high H₂ pressures were avoided through the use of Ni- or Cu based catalysts with either pure furfural, or diluted in water or secondary alcohols [16–18]. Additionally, Group VIII metals have also been used in a FUR-to-FAL conversion. However, the selectivity significantly drops with the increase of the reaction temperature (< 200 °C) [19,20]. Although the carbonyl group is more readily hydrogenated, the furanyl ring can also be hydrogenated with the use of group VIII metals due to their stronger interaction with the unsaturated C-C bonds [21].

The selectivity to the above-mentioned products is highly dependent on the reaction conditions (temperature, pressure, solvent type, concentration) and/or properties of the catalyst (acidity, structure, stability). Therefore, it is of utmost importance to select right conditions, depending on the desired product. One of such examples is the production of alkyl levuliantes, a very important group of chemicals that find their use as solvents, food and fuel additives, fragrances, or as precursors to other value-added products [22]. They are mostly produced by the acid catalyzed conversion of levulinic acid. However, more research

has been devoted to their production from furfural or furfuryl alcohol. Sulfate-containing catalysts have shown high activity and selectivity to alkyl levulinates; Ramli et al [23] used sulfated silica catalysts to obtain a 54 % yield of ethyl levulinate, while Orgino et al [24] used sulfonated carbon catalysts, and Martins et al [25] used commercially available $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ for the production of various alkyl levulinates from levulinic acid dissolved in corresponding alcohol. Tiong et al [26] wrote an extensive review on the production of levulinate esters using ionic liquids, which replace mineral acids and avoid difficult separation and corrosion issues. However, simpler and environmentally friendly catalyst synthesis routes are still sought for.

Similarly, a direct furfural conversion to levulinate esters on a Pt nanoparticles supported on a mesoporous ZrNb binary phosphate solid acid catalyst was carried out at 130 °C, 5 MPa H_2 , for 6 h with high selectivity (75 %) to alkyl levulinates, regardless of the type of alcohol used [27]. Likewise, this is a quite a complicated reaction process involving multistep reactions, while using expensive noble metals and expensive external molecular H_2 . Catalytic transfer hydrogenation (CTH) strategy using alcohols has been proposed as preferable route, as it has been shown that the alcohol not only acts as a solvent and reactant, but can additionally be a hydrogen donor, thus eliminating the need for molecular hydrogen.

Peng et al [28] reported one-pot, multistep reaction using combination of Zr-MCM-41 and Amberlyst-15 catalyst for hydrogenation and subsequent alcoholysis of furfural to various alkyl levulinates. Isopropanol (iProH) has been shown to have the highest yield (85 %), followed by isobutanol and n-butanol with 59.2 and 45.2 %, respectively, while the primary alcohols (methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol) showed yields below 20 %. Similarly, Shide et al. [29] carried out also one-pot conversion of furfural dissolved in isopropanol, over $\text{ZrO}(\text{OH})_2$ and Zr-Mont at 120 °C for 2 h and obtained 7 % furfuryl alcohol, 57 % isopropyl furfuryl ether, and 33 % isopropyl levulinate. Other studies involving multistep reactions with

bifunctional catalysts involve Zr–SBA–15 [30,31] with methanol as solvent, or in isopropanol containing Nb₂O₅–ZrO₂ [32] or Cu–Fe₃O₄ [33] as catalysts. Regardless of the type of metal catalyst used, alcohol solvent, temperature, or reaction time, all studies reported highest selectivities towards alkyl levulinates formed from furfuryl alcohol, with minor yields of corresponding alkyl furfuryl ethers. However, lower activity and selectivity were explained by acetalization reaction or furfural polymerization leading to humins formation, thus, deactivating the catalyst.

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of various parameters on the catalytic activity of molybdenum-based catalysts on the conversion of furfural. First, a catalyst screening through different oxidation states (MoO₂ vs MoO₃) was performed and the activity MoO₃ of three different manufacturers was further investigated. Moreover, the effect of the temperature (170, 185, 200, 215, and 230 °C), catalyst loading (250, 500, 750 mg), reactant concentration (5, 10, 20 wt.%), and hydrogen pressure (20, 35, 50, 65, 80 bar) were studied. Lastly, a reusability study was conducted with third cycle reaction. Additionally, the catalysts have been characterized by nitrogen physisorption to determine the total surface areas, powder X-ray diffraction to determine main planes, as well as with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to examine the morphology. Density functional theory (DFT) was employed for the determination of the amount of active sites per gram of catalyst. The surface energies of the most common low-index surfaces with different terminations were calculated. Based on these results, thermodynamically most probable particle shape was constructed using the Wulff construction, yielding the relative composition. On the most exposed surfaces, adsorption energies of all relevant intermediates, revealing the energies of individual reaction steps, were theoretically calculated to provide further insight into the reaction mechanism.

2. Experimental Part

2.1. Materials

All the reactants, gasses, and catalysts have been purchased from commercial suppliers and used as is, without any further purification. Isopropanol ($\geq 99.5\%$, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany, reference number 107022511), n-butanol ($\geq 98\%$, Honeywell Riedel-de Haën, Seelze, Germany, reference number 11269), and tetrahydrofuran ($>95\text{ wt.}\%$, EMD Millipore, Burlington, MA, USA) were used as solvents, while hydrogen hydrogen (5.0, Messer, Bad Soden am Taunus, Germany) or nitrogen (5.0, Messer, Bad Soden am Taunus, Germany) were used as reaction gases. The later was also used for purging the catalysts and the gas mixtures prior to the catalytic reaction, as well in cleaning the lines after the sample collection. Furfural (98 % Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA, reference number W248908) or furfuryl alcohol (98 %, Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA, reference number 185930) were used as starting reactants. Isopropanol (same as the solvent) was used together with tert-butylbenzene ($\geq 99\%$, Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA, reference number 1421537) as an internal standard for dilution of liquid samples prior to the GC-FID/MS analysis.

Furfuryldeneacetone (98 %, ABCR, Karlsruhe, Germany), furfural (same as the reactant), furfuryl alcohol (same as the reactant), 2-methylfuran anhydrous ($\geq 99\%$, Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA, reference number M46845), acetone ($\geq 99.5\%$, Honeywell Riedel-de Haën, Seelze, Germany, reference number 179124) were used for external calibration. All other isopropyl ether compounds for external calibration were prepared in-house by reacting the corresponding compound with HCl (37 %, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany, reference number 100317), confirming its purity, and back-calculating their concentrations with respect to their corresponding MS-FID peak areas. The catalysts tested involved MoO₃ (FluoroChem, Hadfield, UK, reference number 494341), MoO₃ (99.9 %, ABSCO Limited, Haverhill, UK,

reference number 55797), MoO₃ (99.5 %, Honeywell Fluka, Charlotte, NC, USA, reference number 267856), MoO₂ (97 %, Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA, reference number 711209) which were all used as obtained, with prior overnight oven-drying at 110 °C.

Field-emission scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (SUPRA 35 VP, Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany) was used to investigate structural characteristics of tested materials catalysts. Structural and surface characteristics of used catalysts have also been analyzed by atomic resolution scanning transmission electron microscope (AR STEM, Jeol, ARM 200 CF, Japan), equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) for elemental identification/quantification. Nitrogen physisorption was conducted using Micromeritics ASAP 2020 apparatus (Micromeritics, Norcross, GA, USA). Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method was used for determining total surface areas. Particle size distribution with corresponding particle chord lengths have been analyzed with Focused Beam Reflectance Measurement (FBRM, Lasentec D600 tip L, Metler Toledo, USA). Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded using PW3040/60 X'Pert PRO MPD diffractometer which was operated at 35 kV and 45 mA with CuK_α radiation source ($\lambda = 0.154056$ nm), Ni filter for the absorption of the K_β radiation, and the recording step size of 0.034° in the 2 θ range from 8 to 80° (integration time of 100 sec). JCPDS database was used for determination of crystalline phases from the obtained diffraction peaks. Further detailed information regarding the apparatuses and methodologies can be found in Supplementary Information.

2.2. Catalytic Experiments

All hydrotreatment experiments were carried out in Parr 5000 Multi Reactor System with six 75 mL parallel batch reactors and individual temperature and pressure controls. Agitation was done with magnetic stirrers at 1200 min⁻¹ (but also at 600–1400 min⁻¹ to evaluate the contribution of external mass transfer limitations). Liquid-phase samples were withdrawn through dip-tube, filtered using syringe filters (0.20 μ m), and analyzed by gas

chromatography (GC) (Shimadzu, GCMS-QP2010 Ultra, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with the capillary column (60 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm, Zebron ZB-5, Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). The samples were collected upon preparation of the desired solution (prior to the addition of the catalyst), then, after the set temperature was reached, and further on once every hour of the reaction. Identification of obtained components was done with gas chromatography equipped with mass spectrophotometer (GC-MS), while the quantifications was done with gas chromatography equipped with flame ionization detector (GC-FID), with external calibration. In addition to filtering, sample preparation also involved diluting the sample twenty times in isopropanol containing tert-butyl benzene as an internal standard. For more accurate measurements, dilution factors of the sample itself and internal standard were monitored for correcting preparation and injection inaccuracies, and accordingly applied in calculations of the obtained concentrations. Additionally, the obtained concentrations were either expressed as are in the modelling section, or in terms of conversion of furfural or yields of obtained product, for which Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) have been used, respectively.

Before each catalytic test, all catalysts were dried overnight in the oven at 110 °C. A typical catalytic experiment was carried out with 45 mL of 10 wt.% furfural in isopropanol and 500 mg of dried catalyst. Besides isopropanol being suggested by Peng et al. [28] as the most promising choice of solvent, in this work other solvents (n-butanol and tetrahydrofuran) have been tested as well. No activity has been observed from the reaction in tetrahydrofuran (THF), while comparable activity has been obtained with using n-butanol and isopropanol as solvents. However, in reactions using n-butanol, due to the various isomers of butanol, corresponding alkyl levulinates have been obtained with each of the butanol isomers, thus the selectivity has been significantly lowered, thus isopropanol has been decided to be the most optimal choice of solvent. Preliminary tests were conducted with 15 wt.% furfural in isopropanol, 50 bar of H₂ pressure, and 500 mg of dried catalyst, using a 125–175–225 °C

temperature program with 90 min at each temperature, and sample collection at the beginning and the end of each step. All other catalytic experiments to study effects of temperature, pressure, catalyst loading, and reactant concentration, on catalysts activity and selectivity were performed by heating-up the reactor content (7 K min^{-1}) to a single temperature plateau, that was maintained for 5 h. Detailed operating conditions are shown in Table S1 (see the Supplementary Material).

$$X_{FUR} = \frac{c_{FUR,0} - (c_{FUR,t} + c_{diPMF,t})}{c_{FUR,0}} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

$$Y_x = \frac{c_{FUR,0} - c_{x,t}}{c_{FUR,0}} \times 100 \% \quad (2)$$

Where:

$c_{FUR,0}$ is the initial concentration of furfural stoichiometrically calculated

$c_{FUR,t}$ is the concentration of furfural at time t

$c_{diPMF,t}$ is the concentration of diisopropoxymethylfuran at time t

$c_{x,t}$ is the concentration of product x obtained at time t

2.3. Theoretical calculations methodology

Density functional theory calculations (DFT) were performed in Quantum Espresso 6.4.1 [34,35] using the plane-wave PWscf code. The projector augmented wave method using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzenhof (PBE) [36] exchange correlation pseudopotential [37] was used. Preliminary spin-polarized calculations showed that the magnetic moments are quenched. The Gaussian smearing of 0.05 Ry was applied. To account for a poor description of dispersion interactions by plain DFT [38], the Grimme-D3 correction [39] was used.

Based on convergence testing, the kinetic energy cut off for wave functions was set at 55 Ry and the kinetic energy cut off for charge density was set at 400 Ry. The unit cells (MoO_2 and MoO_3) were sampled with a Monkhorst-Pack mesh [40] using $16 \times 16 \times 16$ K points. For slab

geometries, a 2x2x1 mesh sufficed due to large supercells. To avoid spurious interactions between the periodic slabs, a 14 Å vacuum in the z direction and the standard dipole correction [41] was employed.

For slab calculations, a 2x3 MoO₂ and 1x3 (for 100) or 2x2 (for 111) MoO₃ supercells were used to minimize lateral interactions while keeping the computational time reasonable. To account for all possible adsorption sites, several configurations were probed. The adsorption energies of the reactants, intermediates and products were calculated as

$$\Delta E_{ads} = E_{species+slab} - E_{slab} - E_{species} \quad (3)$$

where $E_{species+slab}$ denotes the energy of the slab with an adsorbate, E_{slab} is the energy of the empty slab and $E_{species}$ is the energy of the adsorbate in gaseous phase (relaxed).

A Wulff construction [42] was also performed for both MoO₂ and MoO₃ to provide the information on the most favorable and exposed surfaces. A Wulff particle can be constructed according to the following equation:

$$d_{hkl} = C \cdot \gamma_{hkl} \quad (4)$$

where d_{hkl} represents the distance from the origin, C is a constant for all surfaces and γ_{hkl} is the surface energy of a (hkl) surface [43]. Generally speaking, higher index surfaces exhibit higher surface energies, which means that they either represent a small fraction of total surface or are not present at all. The equilibrium particle is therefore mostly constructed from surfaces with low Miller indices [43]. We follow the approach from Tian et al. [44] for asymmetric and non-stoichiometric slabs. The surface energy is defined as:

$$\gamma = (E_{cle} + E_{rel})/A \quad (5)$$

where E_{cle} is the cleavage energy and E_{rel} is the relaxation energy. The cleavage energy is defined as:

$$E_{cle} = (E_{unrelax} - n \cdot E_{bulk})/2 \quad (6)$$

where $E_{unrelax}$ is the total energy of unrelaxed slab, n represents the number of repeating bulk units and E_{bulk} is the total energy of a bulk unit cell.

$$E_{rel}(T1) = E_{T1relax} - E_{unrelax} \quad (7)$$

$$E_{rel}(T2) = E_{T2relax} - E_{unrelax} \quad (8)$$

where $E_{rel}(T1)$ is the energy of relaxed T1 termination surface, $E_{T1relax}$ is the energy where T1 is relaxed, whereas T2 is not. We then use the values of E_{cle} and $E_{rel}(T1)$ in Eq. (5) to obtain the surface energy for a certain termination, which can then be used for the Wulff construction as described before.

The adsorption modes are visualized in xCrysDen [45], while the Wulff construction was done in Nanocrystal [46] and visualized in Avogadro [47].

3. Microkinetic Model

The model is used to describe the three-phase (solid catalyst, liquid reactants and solvent, gaseous H₂/N₂) system while considering the hydrogen solubility, adsorption and desorption of all components on and from the catalyst surface, and the corresponding reaction kinetics on the catalyst surface. The above mentioned reaction mechanism, shown in Scheme 1 has been used for mathematical calculations of the set of differential equations used for further solving of all the kinetic rates and concentrations of analogous components. The grey-colored compounds shown in Scheme 1, were not detected in any of our experiments. The proposed reaction network has been used to determine the modeled values of component concentrations while taking in consideration the following assumptions:

- 1) Although some acetalization was present even in the absence of the catalyst, it was considered insignificant, therefore, for the sake of modeling all the reactions are considered occurring heterogeneously, on the surface of the catalyst,
- 2) All vacant sites are considered equivalent and independent of the overall coverage,
- 3) The amount of active sites were determined by DFT calculations, i.e. Wulff construction,
- 4) Only one organic molecule or the hydrogen atom can be adsorbed on the active site as they competitively adsorb,
- 5) Due to the similarity of their structure, adsorption and desorption rate constants for all the organic components have been considered equivalent,
- 6) Hydrogen solubility in 2-propanol has been used to represent its solubility in the liquid phase and was calculated using Henry's constant (Eq. 16) obtained from the work of Jaatinen et al [48],
- 7) Since extensive coke formation has been evident, and numerous dimers and oligomers have been detected, for the sake of simplicity of the model, the remaining mass balance has been accounted as 'REST' and considered to be formed from FUR, (k15), therefore, its concentration is considered to be the amount of moles of furanic compounds per liter,
- 8) Since some difference in the mass balance has been evident even in the first sample before the heat-up, all the concentrations of the observed products have been multiplied by the same factor, such that the beginning mass balance is at 100%. This can be explained by the changing response of the GC detector over time, with respect to the response when the calibration curves have been prepared.

The rates of adsorption (r_j^{ads}), desorption (r_j^{des}), and surface reaction rate (r_i^{surf}), for each compound j and reaction step i are shown in Eq. (9-11), respectively. The adsorption

rate for each compound j is dependent on the adsorption rate constant (k_j^{ads}), the corresponding compound's concentration in the liquid phase (C_j^L), and the coverage of vacant sites (θ_{VS}). The desorption rate of each compound, similarly, depends on the desorption rate constant (k_j^{des}), and the fraction of active sites (θ_j) the corresponding compound occupies. The surface reaction rate depends on the surface reaction rate constant (k_i^{surf}) and the coverage of the corresponding reactants j (θ_j) and l (θ_l).

$$r_j^{ads} = k_j^{ads} \cdot C_j^L \cdot \theta_{VS} \quad (9)$$

$$r_j^{des} = k_j^{des} \cdot \theta_j \quad (10)$$

$$r_i^{surf} = k_i^{surf} \cdot \theta_j \cdot \theta_l \quad (11)$$

Constant automatic recording of temperature and pressure in *Parr* 5000 reactor system during the entire duration of each experiment allowed us to calculate the mass transfer constants, the influence of hydrogen solubility, reaction rate constants, and adsorption and desorption rate constants, at conditions for any given time step. The Arrhenius law was used to describe the reaction rate constants on the temperature, and it is shown through the Eq. (12).

$$k_i^{surf}(T_2) = k_i^{surf}(T_1) \times \exp\left(\frac{Ea_i}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2}\right)\right) \quad (12)$$

The concentration of compound j in the liquid phase was calculated from the Eq. (13) which is shown as a general expression, where V is the total volume of the liquid phase, which was calculated to be 45 mL and n_{TS} is the surface concentration of active sites, determined as described in Section 3.1.

$$\frac{dC_j^L}{dt} = -r_j^{ads} + r_j^{des} \frac{n_{TS}}{V} \quad (13)$$

Differential equation for calculating the concentration of H₂ in the liquid phase is shown in Eq. (14), while for the gas phase in Eq. (15), where $k_{GL}a$ is stirring speed-dependent term, which was obtained from our previous work [49], V_G is the headspace volume of the whole reaction (140 mL), p_{H_2} is the partial pressure of hydrogen in the gas phase, $C_{H_2}^L$ is the concentration of hydrogen in the reaction mixture, and the plus or minus sign suggest formation or the consumption of H₂ in the corresponding phase, respectively.

$$\frac{dC_{H_2}^L}{dt} = +k_{GL}a \left(\frac{p_{H_2}}{H} - C_{H_2}^L \right) - r_j^{ads} + r_j^{des} \frac{n_{TS}}{V} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{dC_{H_2}^G}{dt} = -k_{GL}a \left(\frac{p_{H_2}}{H} - C_{H_2}^L \right) \frac{V_L}{V_G} \quad (15)$$

Where H is Henry's constant obtained for the hydrogen solubility in isopropanol and is expressed as:

$$H = 1573 \times e^{-0.005560 \cdot T} \quad (16)$$

The coverage of the active sites has been obtained from the expression shown in Eq. (17)

$$\frac{d\theta_j}{dt} = r_j^{ads} \frac{V}{n_{TS}} + r_j^{des} + \sum_i^I \pm r_i^{surf} \quad (17)$$

For all the reactions i -s (I is their number) that consume or form j (J is their number). The vacant active site coverage was balanced with the consideration of Eq. (18).

$$\frac{d\theta_{vs}}{dt} = \sum_j^J r_j^{ads} \frac{V}{n_{TS}} + \sum_j^J r_j^{des} + \sum_i^I (\pm r_i^{surf}) \quad (18)$$

For all compounds j -s (J is their number) that adsorb or desorb and for all reactions i -s (I is their number) that have unstoichiometric balance of sites. If the reactant-product molar

ratio is always 1-1 or 2-2, then the last sum can be omitted. System of ordinary differential equations were solved numerically in Matlab 2019b software by using ode23tb algorithm, while kinetic parameters were optimized by Nelder-Mead method to fit modeled values to the experimental counterparts.

3.1. Determination of Active Sites

As the number of active sites is an important piece of information in catalysis, it is determined both experimentally and computationally. With DFT, we calculated the number of active sites per m^2 for different surfaces, which gives us in conjunction with the information gathered from BET the total number of active sites per gram of catalyst.

As N_2 is mostly used as the easiest adsorbate when performing BET, we studied its adsorption. Preliminary testing showed that N_2 binds to surface Mo atoms. In Fig. 1, we show how N_2 can adsorb at the MoO_2 (111) surface.

Fig. 1. Adsorption of N_2 on the MoO_2 (111) surface, A represents top view, B side view, and positions 1 and 2 possible adsorption sites. Color code: blue - Mo, red - O, green - N.

There are two possible adsorption sites (labelled 1 and 2 in Fig. 1). The site 1 has a greater affinity for N_2 , which is suggested both by the adsorption energy (-0.92 eV and -0.11 eV, respectively) and the adsorbate distance to the Mo atom. In configuration 1 that distance is 2.06 Å, while in the case 2, it is almost doubled of that, at 3.91 Å. While the adsorption

energy at site 1 indicates a molecular chemisorption, the interaction of N₂ at site 2 is much lower, corresponding to a weak physisorption. Thus, site 1 is a predominant active site.

Fig. 2. Adsorption of N₂ on MoO₂ (100) surface with A: oxygen termination and B: Mo termination. Colour code: blue - Mo, red – O, green - N.

The MoO₂ (100) surface was constructed with oxygen and with molybdenum termination, and is presented in Fig. 2. On the oxygen-terminated surface, the N₂ molecule is tilted and significantly further away from the molybdenum (3.90 Å). On the molybdenum-terminated surface, the molecule is horizontally placed and 2.09 Å from the Mo atoms. The corresponding adsorption energies are -0.04 and -1.58 eV, respectively, meaning that the oxygen-terminated surface is unreactive towards N₂. This means that experimental BET analysis only shows the exposed Mo sites.

Furthermore, based on the DFT calculations, the number of active sites per m² for the investigated and most prominent surfaces in the Wulff construction is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Calculated active sites per m² for investigated and most prominent surfaces.

Catalytic surface	Active sites / m ²
MoO ₂ (100)	7.40 · 10 ¹⁸
MoO ₂ (111)	3.13 · 10 ¹⁸
MoO ₂ (001)	4.12 · 10 ¹⁸
MoO ₃ (100)	1.26 · 10 ¹⁸
MoO ₃ (111)	2.31 · 10 ¹⁸

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Characterization

The XRD patterns of four mainly investigated catalysts are shown in Fig. 3, with MoO₂ shown in yellow, MoO₃-F in red, MoO₃-A in black, and MoO₃-H shown in green. Clear differences of diffraction peaks are evident between MoO₃ samples and MoO₂ sample, while all the MoO₃ samples have identical diffraction patterns (at the same 2 θ angles). MoO₃-F and MoO₃-A have also identical intensities, while MoO₃-H has slightly higher intensities, which suggests higher crystallinity. Identical diffraction angles for MoO₃ samples are also observed in the literature, and according to Schuh et al. [50] 2 θ angles of 12.7°, 23.3°, 25.7°, 27.3°, and 33° represent the following planes respectively: (020), (110), (040), (021), and (111). Additionally, they noted that peaks at 2 θ = 12.7°, 25.7°, and 38.9° belong to 0k0 reflections and describe rod-like morphology (which was corroborated by the theoretical Wulff construction, see below). The observed variations in ratios of peak intensities among MoO₃ catalysts can be explained through either the presence of preferential orientation of certain planes, or through the possibility that within each type of the catalyst exists non-homogeneous crystal shape, thus the presence of different macrocrystallinity in each of the MoO₃ sources give different ratios among the present planes. Since no decrease in certain plain intensities has been observed due to the preferential orientation of other plains, one can assume the second possibility to be more likely. Additionally, this can be confirmed by observing wider perspective of the image obtained using SEM analysis. As shown in Fig. S1 (see the Supplementary Material), one can observe various forms of particles with inhomogeneous shapes. Although particles are not ideal rods, one can still observe slight elongations along c-axis, thus rod-like structures can be assumed.

Fig. 3. Diffractograms of the four catalysts of interest: MoO₂ (yellow), MoO₃-F (red), MoO₃-A (black), and MoO₃-H (green).

Phase identification of the obtained diffractograms was conducted using the X'Pert HighScore Plus software. Out of 80 % of the identified MoO₂ catalyst, it was found to be 95.2 % MoO₂ and 4.8 % Mo_{5.26}O_{18.62}, as shown in Fig. S2a (see the Supplementary Material). The remaining unidentified 20 %, is believed to be MoO₃, however, those peaks have large shifts, and thus this claim is less reliable. Using the Scherrer equation, the crystalline size was calculated to be 127 nm, and strain 0.172 %. In contrast, all three MoO₃ samples were identified to be 100 % pure MoO₃, with crystalline sizes of 183.2, 361, and 499 nm for MoO₃-A, MoO₃-F, and MoO₃-H, respectively. As shown in Fig. S2b-d, (see the Supplementary Material) although not all peaks for these samples are matched, they still have corresponding peaks in the database files, however, with slight shifts. Consequently, these few shifted peaks cause inaccuracies in strain and crystalline size calculations. The observed shifts can be explained by the presence of stress/strain on the lattice. The lack of grinding of the catalysts prior to their diffraction analysis could leave mechanical strains present in the texture, which is also evident by the location of the shifted peaks, as compression is mostly expressed by the shifts at higher angles [51,52].

Nitrogen physisorption was used for investigating textural properties of the four catalysts. The four catalysts of interest, MoO₃-F, MoO₃-H, MoO₃-A, and MoO₂ have been analyzed and their specific surface areas are found to be 0.9, 0.7, 3.0, and 2.8 m² g⁻¹. The second measurement confirmed that the relative experimental error of was upto 5%. Additionally, their pore volumes are also found to be extremely low, <0.015 cm³ g⁻¹, therefore, none of these materials display any significant porosity. Wawata [53] also reported similarly low (0.6 m² g⁻¹) surface areas found in commercial unsupported MoO₃ catalysts, with slightly higher surface areas (4.9 m² g⁻¹) for the in-house prepared catalysts. However, other studies have reported surface areas of unsupported MoO₃ catalysts to be primarily dependent on the variety of starting precursor and/or the synthesis route involved, and range from <1 to 45 m² g⁻¹ [50,54,55]. Additionally, the catalyst's morphology is likewise dependent on the synthesis route and various synthesis approaches thus yield plethora diverse forms. MoO₃ is mostly found as the stable layered orthorhombic structure α -MoO₃. Parviz et al. [55] described it as covalently-bonded layers of MoO₆ octahedra running along the (100) and (001) directions and bonded by Van der Waals forces in the (010) direction. The shape of the crystals is stab-like due to the exposed (010) face during the crystal growth.

Fig. 4. SEM images of MoO₃-H (A), MoO₃-F (B), MoO₃-A (C), and MoO₂ (D).

The morphology as well as the porosity (or the lack-of), are also visualized by the SEM images shown in Fig. 4. As suggested by their surface areas mentioned above, the low porosity of MoO₃-H and MoO₃-F are also seen in Fig. 4A, and Fig. 4B respectively, where they possess almost perfect crystal-like structure. On the contrary, MoO₃-A and MoO₂, shown in Fig. 4C, and Fig. 4D, show more plate-like and amorphous crystallite structures with the surface of the catalysts displaying some porosity, which was also suggested by the nitrogen physisorption. From the SEM images, it was also possible to obtain information on the mean particle sizes of the four catalysts, and they were measured to be 2 – 4, 10 – 15, 80 – 100, and 60 – 80 μm for MoO₃-F, MoO₃-H, MoO₃-A, and MoO₂, respectively. From these results, it cannot be generalized that the lower particle size necessarily retains lower surface areas, or *vice versa*, however, it can be seen that the two catalysts with the lower surface areas (MoO₃-F and MoO₃-H) have drastically lower mean particle size than the other two

catalysts with higher surface areas ($\text{MoO}_3\text{-A}$ and MoO_2). These results, once again can be ascribed to the different, yet unknown, synthesis routes and/or unlike starting precursors.

To estimate the most prominent surfaces, we performed the Wulff construction on MoO_x , which yielded the thermodynamically most probable particle shapes. First, the calculated surface energies are listed in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2. DFT-calculated surface energy values for MoO_2 in J m^{-2} .

MoO_2	Surface energy / J m^{-2}
(001)	1.17
(010)	3.62
(011)	2.81
(100)	3.62
(101)	2.96
(110)	2.24
(111)	1.24

As shown in Table 2, the (111) and (001) surfaces exhibit the lowest energies (1.24 and 1.17 J m^{-2} , respectively). Other surfaces have significantly higher energies; for instance, (110) has a surface energy of 2.24 J m^{-2} . This strongly suggests that the most prominent surfaces on MoO_2 are (001) and (111).

Table 3 shows the calculated surface energies for MoO_3 . The lowest calculated surface energy was that of the (101) surface with 0.21 J m^{-2} followed by the (001) and (111) surfaces. The differences are smaller than for MoO_2 , meaning that much more surfaces can manifest, depending on the synthesis and operating conditions. Strictly thermodynamically speaking, (101) should be the most prominent followed by (001) and (111).

Table 3. Surface energy values for MoO_3 in J m^{-2} , obtained by means of DFT.

MoO_3 plane	Surface energy / J m^{-2}
(001)	0.34

(010)	3.11
(011)	1.00
(100)	1.14
(101)	0.21
(110)	0.74
(111)	0.58

Fig. 5. Wulff construction for A) a MoO₂ particle with most prominent surfaces (001) and (111) and B) a MoO₃ particle with most prominent surfaces (101) and (111).

The specific surface energy plays a crucial role in the Wulff construction as it determines which surfaces are most exposed based on thermodynamics (ignoring kinetic effects). A schematic representation of the results is shown in Fig. 5.

The results suggested that in the case of MoO₂ (Fig. 5A), the most prominent surfaces are (001) and (111), which represent 7.25 % and 92.75 % of the entire particle, respectively. In the case of MoO₃ (Fig. 5B), (101) and (111) are the most exposed surfaces. The (111) surface represents 20.78 %, while (101) is the remaining 79.22 %.

From these values and values from Table 1, we were able to calculate the number of active sites per m², which were $3.20 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $2.36 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ for MoO₂ and MoO₃, respectively. The theoretical calculations agree well with the experimental results (Fig. 3). For the case of MoO₂, we can observe two distinct peaks. This agrees well with the theoretical Wulff construction, predicting the only exposed surfaces (111) and (001). For the

case of MoO₃ five distinct peaks are evident, corresponding to (020), (110), (040), (021), and (111). In our study, the (111) surface was identified, while (021) was not investigated. (020) and (040) surfaces are not differentiated from (010) in the theoretical Wulff construction.

4.2. Catalytic Activity

4.2.1. Proposed Reaction Mechanism

For easier understanding of all possible reaction pathways and observed products, the proposed reaction mechanism is shown in Scheme 1. Furfural (FUR) was found to form diisopropoxymethylfuran (diPMF) in a reversible reaction, when in contact with isopropanol, even at room temperature and without the use of the catalyst. Further, FUR converts to furfuryl alcohol (FAL), which immediately gets consumed and forms isopropyl furfuryl ether (IFE) and isopropyl levulinate (IPL). At first, it was suggested that IPL gets converted only from FAL, while IFE is an end product and does not get consumed. However, after performing an experiment with FAL as a starting reactant, shown in Fig. S3 (see the Supplementary Material), it was found that after full consumption of FAL and certain amount of IFE formed, IFE gets completely used up and IPL continually forms, without any additional products or intermediates. Although, no reaction intermediates were observed explaining the preferable reaction route of producing IPL, the literature suggests [56,57] that IPL can get formed from both FAL and IFE, with possible reactions and potential intermediates shown in Scheme 1. Additionally, it was found that IPL further forms alpha-angelica lactone (ALAC) in trace amounts. Lastly, it was found that isopropanol acts as a hydrogen donor and after dehydrogenation, it gets converted to acetone (k_{16}). At temperatures above 175 °C, it was found that acetone reacts with furfural and forms furfuryl acetone in a irreversible reaction (FAC).

Scheme 1. Proposed reaction pathway network for furfural hydrotreatment over bulk MoO_x .

4.2.2. Catalyst Screening

Before conducting experimental reactions, it was primarily established that there are no mass transfer limitations due to inappropriate agitation speed. This was concluded with the results obtained from reactions stirred at 600, 1000, and 1400 min^{-1} , which showed identical results, therefore, it was decided that all further experiments are performed at the agitation rate of 1200 min^{-1} . Operating in the kinetic regime would further suggest that the hydrogen transfer from the gas phase to the catalyst surface (or its evolution there from hydrogen donor solvent) is orders of magnitude faster than the surface kinetics, which determines the overall kinetic rates. The preliminary studies included screening of commercially available molybdenum-oxide catalysts: MoO_2 and three MoO_3 provided by different manufacturers, as well as Mo_2C , WO_3 and an industrial hydrotreatment catalyst ($\text{NiMo}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$). Catalytic activities with conversion of FUR and yields of the four most important product (IPL, IFE, FAC, and ALAC) obtained from $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$, MoO_2 , $\text{MoO}_3\text{-H}$, and $\text{MoO}_3\text{-A}$ catalysts are shown in Fig. 6. All four catalysts have shown insignificantly different selectivities towards the same products. Fig. 6 shows that results obtained after 4.5 h reaction with a consecutive 1.5 h steps at 125, 175, and 225 $^\circ\text{C}$ and H_2 pressure of 50 bar, all four catalysts have resulted

in conversion of FUR between 69.1 and 71 %, and yields of IPL, IFE, FAC, and ALAC in the ranges 8.7 – 10.4, 6 – 7.2, 2.6 – 3.9, and 1.0 – 1.4 %, respectively (Fig. S3). It was observed that the reversible product diPMF is present even at room temperature without the presence of catalysts, and is then being consumed with the time. Therefore, for the calculation of conversion of furfural, at time t , the concentration of diPMF was added to the concentration of FUR, since they are reversible compounds. Additionally, many articles on FUR/FAL alcoholysis only mention presence of various and abundant side products that react with the corresponding alcohol, but only few identify diPMF. Consequently, Teixeira et al. [58] and Rubio-Caballero et al. [59] reported diPMF forming at room temperature, however in the presence of the acidic catalyst, while only Koehle et al. [60] reported its formation without the catalyst at room temperature. Furfuryl alcohol (FAL) has also been identified, however, at very low amounts (< 1 %), while at lower temperatures the concentrations were slightly higher. As it can be seen from the temporal representation of sample collection (at the beginning and end of each temperature step), shown in Fig. S3 (see the Supplementary Material), all catalysts show activity at the end of 175 °C section, which further significantly increased with the increase of reaction temperature to 225 °C.

Fig. 6. Catalyst screening results obtained from 500 mg of four catalysts used, MoO₃-F, MoO₂, MoO₃-A, and MoO₃-H, in temperature gradient reaction involving 1.5 h at each temperature step of 125, 175, and 225 °C. Results shown represent conversion of 10 wt.-% FUR, and yields of IPL, IFE, FAC, FAL, and ALAC, at the end of the reaction.

These catalysts were further compared to the activity of commercially available Mo₂C, WO₃, and MoO₃-NiO/Al₂O₃, and as shown in Table S2 (see the Supplementary Material), the results are significantly different. The final conversion of furfural over Mo₂C reached 37.2 %, with IPL having the lowest yield, 2.5 %, and FAL the largest, 12.2 %. Worth noting is the mass balance (87.5 %) which is quite higher when compared to other reactions. The test over WO₃ has shown conversion of 11.8 % with highest yield of IFE, 6.3 %, while IPL, FAL, and diPMF all had below 1 %. Surprisingly, the supported MoO₃-NiO/Al₂O₃ catalysts has shown conversion of 54.5 % with the IPL yield only of 9.2 % and IFE of 9.4 %, while the mass balance was at 72.1 % after 5 hours. Therefore, it was concluded that bulk MoO_x catalysts are significantly more active and selective for FUR hydrotreatment in isopropanol, and were subjected to further investigation.

4.2.3. Temperature Effect

After the two most active catalysts (MoO_2 and $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$) have been identified, they have been selected for further analysis of their activity at various temperatures (isothermal conditions). Experimental (symbols) and modeled (lines) concentrations of products obtained in the liquid phase in 5 hour reactions, at temperature ranging 170 – 230 °C, over $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$ and MoO_2 are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, respectively. The results are as expected: with the increase of temperature the conversion rates are increasing, which range from 23.3 % at 170 °C to 68.6 % at 230 °C for MoO_2 catalyst, while for $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$ the conversions ranged from 16 % at 170 °C to 76.2 % at 230 °C. Also, the yields of all products are increasing both temporally and with an increase of the reaction temperature; however, the increase is relatively small for a relatively large temperature range, as activation energies of all rate-determining steps (i.e. E_{a3} , E_{a5}) are relatively low. As shown in Fig. 7f, IPL yields are ranging from 3.2 % at 170 °C to 18.0 % at 230 °C for $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$, and for MoO_2 , shown in Fig. 8f, from 4.4 % at 170 °C to 17.4 % at 230 °C (all yields obtained at the end of the reaction, after 5 h). Both catalysts, yet again, show insignificantly different results with respect to the same reaction temperature, as well as with respect of the time of sample collection. An interesting observation was made for the reversible product diPMF, which at each reaction temperature would have the highest yield after the first hour, after which it would eventually nearly diminish. Also, the higher the reaction temperature would be, the lower concentration of diPMF would be observed. Therefore, what was concluded from these experiments, and also reactions shown in Fig. S3, is that the acetalization of FUR into diPMF is preferred prior to hydrogenation and/or etherification, regardless of the reaction temperature. This can be explained through the mesomeric (resonance) effect which makes the aldehyde on FUR a highly electron withdrawing group.

Fig. 7. Temperature influence a) 170 °C b) 185 °C, c) 200 °C, d) 215 °C, e) 230 °C, f) yields of IPL obtained under reaction temperatures mentioned previously. Meaning of symbols: ■ FUR, ● diPMF, ★ IPL, ▲ IFE, ● FAL, ◆ FAC, ▼ ALAC, ▲ Rest, - - - - temperature. Graph f) shows IPL yields obtained under ★ 230 °C, ★ 215 °C, ★ 200 °C, ★ 185 °C, and ★ 170 °C. Lines correspond to the model, while the scatters correspond to the experimental data points, both matching in color (500 mg MoO₃-F, 50 bar H₂, 10 wt.% FUR, 5 h).

From the reactions involving temperature gradient shown in Fig. S3, it was found that furfuryl acetone starts being formed at the higher end of the 1.5 h of 175 °C section and is then continually being formed at higher temperatures. This was confirmed with the isothermal reaction of both catalysts (Fig. 7 and Fig. 8), where there was no FAC found (< 1 %) in the reaction at 170 °C (Fig. 7a, and Fig. 8a), while during reactions under higher

temperatures, it is present in significantly higher concentrations at any point of the reaction. Additionally, it was noted that the carbon balance shows a negative trend with the increase of temperature. MoO₃-F after 5 h reaction at 170 °C showed 93.2 % while at 230 °C it was at 57.6 %, and for MoO₂ at 170 °C the carbon balance was at 82.9 % while at 230 °C it was at 57.4 %. This is visualized in Fig. 7-8 with yellow marks, where the remaining mass needed for the complete closure of the mass balance is continually increasing with increased reaction temperature. The remaining mass balance can be attributed to the evident coke (humins) formed on the walls of the reactor, magnetic stirrers, and the catalysts themselves, as well as to the identified traces of FUR/FAL and IPL dimers, that have not been quantified.

For both catalysts, all the products are continually increasing with time under reaction temperatures of 170, 185, 200, and 215 °C. However, under 230 °C, IFE (cyan) was noticed to start diminishing closer to the end of the reaction time, thus confirming that it is the main intermediate towards the production of IPL. FAL (green), which was the initial step towards the IPL production and a precursor to IFE, can be seen to be missing during the entire length of reaction under temperature of 170 °C. Additionally, it was noticed that as higher the reaction temperature was, FAL was observed earlier into the reaction, as well as in higher concentrations. However, the concentrations were still very low throughout the reaction comparing to the remaining compounds, suggesting fast etherification to IFE, which was also confirmed by Zhu et al. [61]. These results suggest reaction k_3 to be the rate determining step. This statement, as well as for the sake of confirming the suggested reaction mechanism, an additional reaction has been carried out with identical reaction conditions, while instead of FUR, 10 wt.% of FAL has been used as a starting reactant. The results shown in Fig. S4 (see the Supplementary Material), are as expected: 64.2 % of FAL gets consumed initially after the heat-up, while after one hour into the reaction it diminishes completely. Additionally, IFE is found to have the highest yield of 11.8 % after the heat-up, after which it diminishes

completely after 2 hours, thus confirming that the k_3 is the rate determining step, and that both FAL and IFE are key intermediates in FUR conversion to IPL. Additionally, this was confirmed through the kinetic data involving all reaction rate constants and activation energies for all the reactions, which are shown in Table 4, where it can be seen that k_3 has the higher activation energy and lowest reaction rate constant. Similar results have been observed from Bernal et al. [33] who found low activity of the catalyst due to FUR coke formation and catalyst deactivation. This was further avoided with 50:50 FUR–FAL mixture, where FAL was completely consumed, while 50 % of FUR remained unreacted. Overall, from these experiments it was shown that both catalysts have insignificantly different activities and selectivities towards same products: diPMF, FAL, IFE, FAC, and IPL, as well as coke and dimers formations, and that the predicted model fits well the experimentally obtained results.

Fig. 8. Temperature influence a) 170 °C b) 185 °C, c) 200 °C, d) 215 °C, e) 230 °C, f) yields of IPL obtained under reaction temperatures mentioned previously. Meaning of symbols: ■ FUR, ● diPMF, ★ IPL, ▲ IFE, ● FAL, ◆ FAC, ▼ ALAC, ▲ Rest, - - - - temperature. Graph f) shows IPL yields obtained under ★ 230 °C, ★ 215 °C, ★ 200 °C, ★ 185 °C, and ★ 170 °C. Lines correspond to the model, while the scatters correspond to the experimental data points, both matching in color (500 mg MoO₂, 50 bar H₂, 10 wt.% FUR, 5 h).

Table 4. Calculated kinetic parameters for FUR hydrotreatment over MoO₂ and MoO₃-F catalysts.

			Reaction rate constants at 200 °C (k_i) / min ⁻¹		Activation energies (E_{a_i}) / J mol ⁻¹		^a TOF _i / min ⁻¹	
i	Products	r_i	MoO ₃ -F	MoO ₂	MoO ₃ -F	MoO ₂	MoO ₃ -F	MoO ₂
1	diPMF, H ₂ O	$k1 \cdot \theta_{FUR} \cdot \theta_{iPrOH}$	$(3.6 \pm 0.3) \cdot 10^5$	$(3.8 \pm 0.3) \cdot 10^5$	$(2.9 \pm 2.9) \cdot 10^3$	$(1.1 \pm 1.1) \cdot 10^4$	$9.6 \cdot 10^2$	$1.5 \cdot 10^4$
2	FUR, iPrOH	$k2 \cdot \theta_{diPMF} \cdot \theta_{VS}$	$(1.3 \pm 0.4) \cdot 10^{10}$	$(4.4 \pm 1.0) \cdot 10^9$	$(3.2 \pm 3.2) \cdot 10^4$	$(3.2 \pm 3.2) \cdot 10^4$	$3.5 \cdot 10^2$	$1.1 \cdot 10^4$
3	FAL	$k3 \cdot \theta_{FUR} \cdot \theta_{H_2}$	$(7.3 \pm 1.6) \cdot 10^2$	$(1.3 \pm 0.1) \cdot 10^2$	$(1.8 \pm 0.3) \cdot 10^5$	$(7.8 \pm 1.4) \cdot 10^4$	$3.2 \cdot 10^1$	5.5
4	IFE, H ₂ O	$k4 \cdot \theta_{FAL} \cdot \theta_{iPrOH}$	$(2.0 \pm 2.0) \cdot 10^5$	$(3.0 \pm 3.0) \cdot 10^5$	$(9.7 \pm 9.7) \cdot 10^3$	$(2.4 \pm 2.4) \cdot 10^2$	$3.1 \cdot 10^1$	5.3
5	MOX	$k5 \cdot \theta_{IFE}$	$(8.3 \pm 1.8) \cdot 10^2$	$(3.5 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^2$	$(1.7 \pm 1.7) \cdot 10^4$	$(7.8 \pm 7.8) \cdot 10^3$	$1.5 \cdot 10^1$	2.2
6	IPL	$k6 \cdot \theta_{MOX} \cdot \theta_{H_2O}$	$\gg k5$	$\gg k5$	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
7	ALAC, iPrOH	$k7 \cdot \theta_{IPL} \cdot \theta_{VS}$	$(9.5 \pm 7.7) \cdot 10^5$	$(4.5 \pm 3.9) \cdot 10^5$	$(1.4 \pm 1.4) \cdot 10^4$	$(3.1 \pm 3.1) \cdot 10^4$	1.4	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-1}$
8	C ₅ H ₇ O ₂ *	$k8 \cdot \theta_{FAL}$	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible	Negligible
9	C ₅ H ₇ O ₂ *	$k9 \cdot \theta_{C_5H_7O_2^*}$	Immediate	Immediate	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
10	IPL	$k10 \cdot \theta_{C_5H_7O_2^*} \cdot \theta_{iPrOH}$	Immediate	Immediate	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
11	MTHF, H ₂	$k11 \cdot \theta_{FAL} \cdot \theta_{H_2}$	Negligible	Negligible	N.A.	N.A.	Negligible	Negligible
12	C ₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ *	$k12 \cdot \theta_{IFE}$	Negligible	Negligible	N.A.	N.A.	Negligible	Negligible
13	C ₅ H ₇ O ₂ *, ^b DEE	$k13 \cdot \theta_{C_8H_{13}O_2^*} \cdot \theta_{iPrOH}$	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
14	FAC	$k14 \cdot \theta_{FUR} \cdot \theta_{ACE}$	$(5.1 \pm 3.2) \cdot 10^2$	$(1.1 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^2$	$(1.5 \pm 0.7) \cdot 10^5$	$(1.1 \pm 0.4) \cdot 10^5$	4.1	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-1}$
15	REST, H ₂ O	$k15 \cdot \theta_{FUR} \cdot \theta_{H_2}$	$(1.1 \pm 0.3) \cdot 10^3$	$(1.8 \pm 0.2) \cdot 10^2$	$(1.7 \pm 0.3) \cdot 10^5$	$(5.6 \pm 1.1) \cdot 10^4$	$4.9 \cdot 10^1$	7.5
16	ACE, H ₂	$k16 \cdot \theta_{iPrOH} \cdot \theta_{VS}$	$(4.3 \pm 1.8) \cdot 10^6$	$(2.7 \pm 1.0) \cdot 10^6$	$(8.3 \pm 1.8) \cdot 10^4$	$(3.4 \pm 2.9) \cdot 10^4$	$8.0 \cdot 10^1$	$2.4 \cdot 10^3$
17	iPrOH	$k17 \cdot \theta_{ACE} \cdot \theta_{H_2}$	$(1.4 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^{-1}$	$(1.1 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^{-2}$	$(1.2 \pm 1.2) \cdot 10^4$	$(2.7 \pm 2.7) \cdot 10^4$	$8.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$

^a Maximum turnover frequencies obtained for reactions under 200 °C
^b DEE – diethyl ether

4.2.4. Catalyst Loading Effect

As $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$ has been identified as slightly more active and selective catalyst, it has been chosen for further investigation. Fig. 9 shows the catalytic activity under identical reaction conditions (200 °C, 50 bar H_2 , 10 wt.% FUR, 5 h) and three different catalyst dosages, 250, 500, and 700 mg of $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$, shown in Fig. 9a, 9b, and 9c, respectively. In Fig. 9d, it has been shown the effect of catalyst loading on the yield of IPL, and the results are as expected; more catalyst results with higher yields of IPL. Also from it, it can be seen that the yield of IPL increased with increasing reaction time for all different catalyst dosages. From the same point of each reaction, the higher the catalyst dosage was, the higher the IPL yield. The yields obtained after 5 h over 250, 500 and 750 mg are 10.8 %, 12.2 %, and 14.2 % respectively. However, the incremental increase of catalyst amount of 250 mg does not consequently increase the yields in the same proportions, i.e. the yields obtained with 500 mg catalysts are not double the yields obtained with 250 mg of catalyst. As the turnover frequency (TOF) is related to the amount of active sites, the obtained yields should be linear with the increasing number of active sites, as it was shown by Chen et al. [30] in FUR alcoholysis in methanol over Zr/SBA-15 catalyst. Although not proportional to the mass of catalyst (active sites) added, the yields obtained after adding more catalyst are matched surprisingly well with our microkinetic model, which revealed that coverages of compounds and subsequent TOFs for reaction 3 and 15 are slightly affected by the overall mass of the catalyst, hence the overall rate of IPL formation is not completely proportional to the catalyst mass.

Fig. 9. Catalyst loading influence a) 250 mg b) 500 mg, c) 750 mg, d) yields of IPL obtained over amounts of catalyst temperatures mentioned previously. Meaning of symbols: ■ FUR, ● diPMF, ★ IPL, ▲ IFE, ● FAL, ◆ FAC, ▼ ALAC, ▲ Rest, - - - temperature. Graph d) shows IPL yields obtained over ★ 750 mg, ★ 500 mg, and ★ 250 mg of MoO₃-F. Lines correspond to the model, while the scatters correspond to the experimental data points, both matching in color (200 °C, 50 bar H₂, 10 wt.% FUR, 5 h).

4.2.5. Reactant Concentration Effect

Further testing involved investigation of starting reactant concentration on activity of the MoO₃-F catalyst. Fig. 10 shows the catalytic activity under identical reaction conditions (200 °C, 50 bar H₂, 500 mg MoO₃-F, 5 h) and three different starting FUR concentrations: 5, 10, and 20 wt.%, shown in Fig. 10a, 10b, and 10c, respectively. Fig. 10d shows yields of IPL measured hourly for 5, 10, and 20 wt.% of furfural in isopropanol, and obtained results suggest that the lower starting concentration of furfural, the higher yields are obtained. After 5 hours, the obtained IPL yield for 20 wt.% FUR was 9.7 %, for 10 wt.% FUR was 12.2 %, and for 5 wt.% FUR it was obtained 19.7 % IPL (reported as absolute yield values, not

relative). Similar observation has been made by Peng et al. [28], Chen et al. [30], and Zhang et al. [57]. However, they all observed that after a certain point of decreasing the reactant concentration, the yields of alkyl levulinate also start decreasing, potentially due to the overly diluted environment, which reduces the probability of the reactant reaching the active site. Additional observation in our study was that regarding the mass balance, which was found to be 59 % after 5 hours of the reaction, under all three reaction conditions. That means that the higher concentration of coke and other unidentified oligomers has been formed for the reactions with higher starting reactant concentrations. Provided that the same amount of catalyst has been used in all three reactions, it is evident that this higher concentration of coke and oligomers blocks the active sites, which then results in such a trend of observed yields.

Fig. 10. Reactant concentration influence a) 5 wt.% b) 10 wt.-%, c) 20 wt.-% FUR, d) yields of IPL obtained from starting FUR concentrations mentioned previously. Meaning of symbols: ■ FUR, ● diPMF, ★ IPL, ▲ IFE, ● FAL, ◆ FAC, ▼ ALAC, ▲ Rest, - - - - temperature. Graph d) shows IPL yields obtained from ★ 20 wt.-%, ★ 10 wt.-%, and ★ 5 wt.-% of FUR. Lines correspond to the model, while the scatters correspond to the experimental data points, both matching in color (200 °C, 50 bar H₂, 500 mg MoO₃-F, 5 h).

When 100 % FUR was tested, the sample collection after the heat-up was not possible, and upon opening the reactor it was evident the entire content has polymerized into dark, solid, sticky matter. Additionally, the 10 % FUR in tetrahydrofural (THF) was tested under the same reaction conditions, and no activity has been observed. When n-butanol has been used as a solvent in the same proportions, the activity was the same as for the isopropanol solvent, however, the selectivity was decreased due to higher impurities and various isomers of butanol. These products were not quantified due to the lack of standards, however, from their mass spectrometry fragments, it was evident that for each isopropyl group observed while using iPrOH as a solvent, an n-propyl group was substituted instead. Lighter alcohols were not tested due to their low boiling point and difficulty of sampling. Consequently, these results suggest that the used alcohol plays a crucial role, primarily as an efficient solvent, as well as a reactant, which defines the obtained end product. Additionally, it is evident that the concentration of the reactant dissolved in the desired solvent affects the activity of the catalyst since the higher concentration of starting reactant causes higher concentrations of produced coke and oligomers, which results in sooner deactivation of the catalyst.

4.2.6. Pressure Effect

Further investigation involved the effect of hydrogen pressure on catalytic activity of $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$. Fig. 11 shows the catalytic activity under identical conditions (200 °C, 10 wt.% FUR, 500 mg $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$, 5 h) and five different H_2 pressures, 20, 35, 50, 65, and 80 bar, shown in Fig. 11a, 11b, 11c, 11d, and 11e, respectively. Fig. 11f shows IPL yields observed hourly for 5 hours, obtained from all five different pressures, and the results show no significant differences. Under the median pressure of 50 bar, the obtained results included the IPL yields of 0.2, 5.0, 7.9, 10.0, 11.0, and 12.2 % for samples collected after the 20 min of temperature ramp, 60, 120, 180, 240, and 300 minutes after the ramp, respectively. All other IPL yields obtained for other reaction pressures fall within the error of 0.5 % IPL yield,

calculated due to technical errors related to the experimental setup. From these results, it is evident that there are no direct correlations nor patterns observed on IPL yields or other products due to hydrogen pressure variations.

Considering that our model incorporates the partial pressure in determining the amount of hydrogen dissolved in iPrOH, which was expected to have a crucial role for the rate determining step of FUR hydrogenation to FAL. By fitting the modeled and experimental concentration values, it can be concluded that the hydrogen pressure has no effect on the overall reaction rate, despite H_2 concentrations in the liquid being significantly different, therefore the H_2 coverage mainly remains unaffected by P, due to extensive H_2 formation on the surface from r_{16} reaction and relatively slow H_2 desorption, which prevents further formation of gaseous H_2 . Reversible k_{17} reaction also helps balancing the H_2 coverage. This was further tested by replacing the hydrogen gas with nitrogen, and the results obtained, shown in Fig. S5 (see the Supplementary Material) confirm this statement. It was shown that the concentrations of all the compounds observed are either identical (overlapped), or fall within the range of a random error (calculated for each compound individually and range 0.08 – 2.5 % of yield or conversion). From these results it can be concluded that no external hydrogen is needed for this reaction as isopropanol acts as hydrogen donor, therefore, making this reaction route safer and more economically viable.

Fig. 11. Pressure influence a) 20 bar, b) 35 bar, c) 50 bar, d) 65 bar, e) 80 bar H₂ pressure, f) yields of IPL obtained under reaction temperatures mentioned previously. Meaning of symbols: ■ FUR, ● diPMF, ★ IPL, ▲ IFE, ● FAL, ◆ FAC, ▼ ALAC, ▲ Rest, ---- temperature. Graph f) shows IPL yields obtained under ★ 80 bar, ★ 65 bar, ★ 50 bar, ★ 35 bar, and ★ 20 bar. Lines correspond to the model, while the scatters correspond to the experimental data points, both matching in color (200 °C, 500 mg MoO₃-F, 10 wt.% FUR, 5 h).

4.2.7. Reusability Study

The MoO₃-F catalyst was subjected to the reusability testing by retrieving the used catalyst after the reaction through filtering, washing it with methanol, deionized water, drying in the oven overnight at 110 °C, and applying it to the second and third cycle of reaction.

After the reaction and filtration, about 15 % of the initially introduced catalyst mass was lost. Therefore, in order to have comparable reaction conditions involving identical catalyst mass, the deficient mass was not compensated with the fresh catalyst, rather additional reaction was conducted under same reaction conditions, and their retrieved catalysts were combined, thus giving sufficient amount of spent catalyst (500 mg) for subsequent reactions. Fig. 12 shows the catalytic results of the three reaction cycles using MoO₃-F with furfural conversion shown in red, and the yields of IPL, IFE, FAC, and ALAC shown in blue, yellow, green, and orange respectively. After the first reaction, the conversion was at 69 % with yields of IPL at 11.9 %, IFE at 7.2 %, FAC at 3.1 %, and ALAC at 1.2 %. After the second and third run, the activity and selectivity were almost identical, however much different from the first run. The conversion dropped down to 38.2 %, with yields of IPL at 4.8 % and IFE at 5.6 %. Only traces of FAC and ALAC were observed, while the cumulative selectivity of hydrogenation route via *r*₃ (evident as IFE and IPL formation) even increased in the 2nd and 3rd cycle, despite a decrease of its reaction rate constant (hence, lower conversion) and corresponding TOF₃. Such trend of decreasing activity has been attributed to the coke formation on the surface of the catalyst, which results in the blockage of active sites and thus lowers the activity of the catalyst. The presence of carbonaceous material on the surface of the catalyst has been verified with TEM-EDX analysis of the used MoO₃-F catalyst, shown in Fig. S6 and Fig. S7 (see the Supplementary Material). From the obtained images, it is clearly visible that large amounts of the particle surface is covered by carbon containing material, instead of the original molybdenum species.

Fig. 12. Reusability study of the $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$ catalysts observed for three consecutive reactions and its effect on the conversion of ■ FUR, and yields of ■ IPL, ■ IFE, ■ FAC, and ■ ALAC. (200 °C, 500 mg $\text{MoO}_3\text{-F}$, 10 wt.% FUR, 5 h).

4.2.8. Theoretical investigation on Reaction Mechanisms

The reaction mechanism was studied on MoO_2 (100) and (111) surfaces, whereas the studied planes for MoO_3 were (101) and (111), which we derived from DFT calculations as the most prominent on respective catalysts (see section 4.1). Several DFT studies on furfural and its derivatives adsorptions were already conducted, such as those by Vorotnikov et al. [62] on the Pd (111) surface, by Sitthisa et al. [63] on the Ni (111) and NiFe (111) surfaces, by Wang et al. [64] on Pd (111) surface. They all reported that furfural and its derivatives are most stable in a flat or slightly tilted configuration, which was tested and confirmed in our work.

Furfural was positioned on several possible surface sites to identify the most stable adsorption mode. The strongest adsorption energies on MoO_2 (111), MoO_2 (100), MoO_3 (111) and MoO_3 (101) are -1.68, -0.60, -1.14, and -0.80 eV, respectively. This shows that (111) surface, in both cases, generally binds furfural stronger than its counterparts. The most stable configuration for both catalysts is shown in Fig. 13.

Table 5. Adsorption energies in eV.

Species	MoO ₂ (100)	MoO ₂ (111)	MoO ₃ (101)	MoO ₃ (111)
FUR	-0.60	-1.68	-0.80	-1.14
FAL	-0.65	-1.46	-1.28	-1.12
IFE	-1.12	-1.21	-1.42	-1.57
MOX	-1.02	-1.90	-1.32	-1.51
IPL	-0.65	-1.86	-1.05	-1.02
ALAC	-0.10	-1.16	-0.80	-0.97

Based on the experimental results, we propose the following reaction mechanism: FUR → FAL → IFE → MOX → IPL → ALAC, where IPL is the desired product, although it is not the only possible pathway, which is clear from Scheme 1. We chose this reaction mechanism as experiments confirmed that IFE is the main intermediate as suggested from the experiment with FAL as a starting reactant, and shown in Fig. S4 (see the Supplementary Material). We calculated the adsorption energies of these intermediates (Table 5) and constructed the potential energy surface (shown in Fig. 14). In general we can observe that (111) surface on MoO₂ binds furfural and intermediates more strongly than (100) facet, whereas the values are comparable between the (111) and (101) facets on MoO₃.

Fig. 13. Furfural adsorption configurations on A: MoO_2 (100), B: MoO_2 (111), C: MoO_3 (101), D: MoO_3 (111), 1 being the side view and 2 top view. Color code: white – H, red – O, grey – C, blue – Mo.

In Fig. 13, stable adsorption of furfural on different surfaces is shown. The adsorption on MoO_2 (100) is the weakest, which is due to the oxygen atoms blocking Mo from being in a

more direct contact with the adsorbate molecules. Similarly, the adsorption energies on MoO_3 (101) and (111) surfaces are slightly more favorable relative to the MoO_2 (100) surface. On MoO_2 (111), the adsorption is most favorable, is stronger, where the adsorbed molecules interact with the surface Mo atoms.

Fig. 14. Potential energy surface for the studied reaction on MoO_2 (100), MoO_2 (111), MoO_3 (101), and MoO_3 (111). The plots are staggered by 6 eV for legibility. Intermediates labelled as in main text. The dash-dotted line represents the undesired pathway.

In Fig. 14, the potential energy surface (PES) for the hydrogenation of FUR is shown. As the reaction network is unwieldy to break down to individual elementary steps, only the reaction energies between the stable intermediates are shown. This still yields important information on the reaction mechanism as reaction barriers (not shown here) are usually strongly correlated with the reaction energies (the fact heavily used in the so-called BEP relations).

The desired product is IPL but ALAC also forms (as evidenced by the experiments). While on MoO₂(111) and MoO₃(111) subsequent conversion of IPL (the desired product) to ALAC is weakly endothermic or exothermic, respectively, the other two surfaces are much less conducive for this reaction. All the intermediates in proposed theoretical pathway except MOX were detected experimentally. The MOX is included because it is mechanistically reasonable to expect its formation, and its quick further reaction. Its adsorption energies are amongst the highest amidst the calculated intermediates, explaining why it does not desorb but quickly reacts further.

It is also clear from the PES diagram that while the reaction follows a similar path, there are some differences. Most notably, the first hydrogenation step of FUR to FAL is probably the rate determining step on MoO₃ as it is the most endothermic (implying a high barrier per BEP correlations). On MoO₂, all steps have comparable reaction energies, which are in general lower. This means that MoO₂ is a better catalyst than MoO₃. To stop the reaction when IPL is formed, the (111) surfaces should be avoided.

5. Conclusions

Catalytic hydrotreatment represents a promising route for the valorization of biomass-derived compounds by upgrading them to target value-added chemicals. This work provides mechanistic and kinetic insight into furfural hydrotreatment in isopropanol, over MoO_x catalysts. A range of reaction conditions has been tested and no significant changes have been observed in the product distribution. Three bulk MoO₃ catalysts obtained from different manufacturers and one MoO₂ catalyst have been tested and they all (in contrast to NiMo/Al₂O₃, Mo₂C and WO₃) showed signs of activity at temperatures above 170 °C, while their activity and selectivity was insignificantly different. Regardless of the selected reaction condition, isopropyl levulinate (IPL) has been identified as the most abundant end product, which was suggested to be formed through the hydrogenation of furfural to furfuryl alcohol,

and subsequent etherification to isopropyl furfuryl ether, from which IPL is formed through ring opening. Furfuryl acetone is found to be formed at temperatures above 175 °C, through aldol condensation of furfural and acetone. The reaction conditions slightly affect yields of obtained products, where it was found that lower concentration of starting reactant, as well as higher amount of catalyst, result in higher yields of the obtained products. Most importantly, it was concluded that hydrogen pressure has no effect, while additionally, its presence is not needed, since isopropanol acts as a hydrogen donor. The obtained kinetic data agree relatively well with the experimentally obtained results, thus providing an in-depth understanding of furfural hydrotreatment.

Density functional theory was used to determine the active sites and to investigate the reaction mechanisms. The Wulff construction was employed to determine the most prominent surfaces of both MoO₂ and MoO₃ catalyst and the particle shape. We then calculated the theoretical fractions of each surface and the concentration of active sites per m² of each catalyst: $3.20 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $2.36 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ for MoO₂ and MoO₃, respectively. The final number of active sites was obtained by combining these values with the BET results, yielding 7.19×10^{-6} and 1.71×10^{-6} active sites for MoO₂ and MoO₃-F catalysts, respectively. Additionally, the reaction mechanism and adsorption strengths were calculated for the reactants, intermediates and products on MoO₂ (100), MoO₂ (111), MoO₃ (101) and MoO₃ (111) surfaces, which revealed that the adsorptions are stronger on surfaces directly exposing Mo atoms (e.g. MoO₂ (111)). From the potential energy surface diagram, it is apparent that the reaction follows a similar path on all surfaces. However, the first step of hydrogenation of FUR to FAL appears to be the rate-limiting step, which agrees well with the experimental data.

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